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DENTAL MORPHOLOGY OF THE PREHISPANIC POPULATION OF OBANDO IN THE YEAR 780 +/- 110 AD IN THE VALLE DEL CAUCA DEPARTMENT, COLOMBIA

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Resumen

Se reporta la frecuencia de manifestación de 23 rasgos discretos dentales de alta significancia genético – taxonómica en 20 individuos, 4 Masculinos, 1 Femenino y 15 Alófosos de la población prehispánica de *Obando* en el Departamento del *Valle del Cauca* en Colombia, portadores de la tradición cultural *Quimbaya Tardío* que existió en el año 780 +/- 110 d.C. (Beta-97700) (Rodríguez y Rodríguez, 1999).

Abstract

This study reports the occurrence frequency of 23 dental discrete traits of high genetic taxonomic significance in 20 individuals, 4 male, 1 female, and 15 Alófosos, from the prehispanic population of *Obando* in the *Valle del Cauca* Department in *Colombia*, carrier of the *Quimbaya Tardío* Cultural Tradition who lived in the year 780 +/- 110 AD (Beta-97700) (Rodríguez and Rodríguez, 1999).

Introduction

Dental Morphology, known in Bioanthropology as the study of discrete dental traits, is a biological aspect which is under a strong genetic control and shows minimal sexual dimorphism which makes it ideal for its use as a genetic marker of human populations (Minkov, 1996; Hillson, 1986, 1996).

Its systematic treatment permits us to build microevolutionary tendencies of human populations through-

out space and time, explaining their genetic stability or instability (homogeneous or heterogeneous genetic flow) from a biocultural perspective, and helping to solve questions of anthropological nature such as the knowledge of the ethnogenesis of ancient and present populations.

There is no documentation in *Colombia* about the special dental morphology in Prehispanic populations in the *Valle del Cauca* Department.

This article registers the occurrence frequency of 23 dental discrete traits in the Prehispanic population of *Obando* in the *Valle del Cauca* Department, carrier of the *Quimbaya Tardío* Cultural Tradition who lived in the year 780 +/- 110 AD (Beta-97700) (Rodríguez and Rodríguez, 1999).

Materials and Methods

170 teeth belonging to 20 individuals, 4 male, 1 female, and 15 Alófosos are the sample used in this study. The teeth came from the primary multiple burial (Perafán, 2000) from the tomb 4 of *Obando*, in the archaeological excavations made in the municipality of *Obando*, in the *Valle del Cauca* Department, *Colombia* (Rodríguez, 1996).

The systematization of the dental traits was carried out following the classification systems suggested by A. A. Zoubov (1997) and C. Turner *et al.* (1991). The statistic calculations used to obtain the adequate averages were made following the procedures suggested by H.

Thomas (1986). The angular transformation of the feature frequencies was done using the Freeman and Tukey equation (1973, in Lloyd-Jones, 1997).

Results

Upper Premolars

1) Roots Number: It is the count of the present roots number. Gradation suggested by Zoubov (1997). 7 of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degrees 1=50%, and 2=50%.

Lower Premolars

2) Roots Number: it is the countdown of the present roots number. Gradation suggested by Tomes (1923 in Turner 1991) and modified by Thomas and Herzog (1979, in Turner *et al.*, 1991). 7 of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degrees 1=100%.

3) Groove Pattern: it is the shape formed by the intercuspid furrows in the occlusal surface. Gradation suggested by Zoubov (1997). 13 of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degrees 1=7,1%, 2=85,8% (See Figure 1), and 3=7,1%.

Upper Molars

4) Metacone: it is the absence or very subtle forms of expression. Gradation suggested by Turner and Kaschner (1978, in Turner *et al.*, 1991). 10 of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degrees 0=10%, 1=10%, 3=5%, 4=25%, and 5=50%.

5) Hypocone: it is the absence or very subtle forms of expression. Gradation suggested by Larson (1975, in Turner *et al.*, 1991) and modified by Turner and Scott (1978, in Turner *et al.*, 1991). 10 of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degrees 1=8,3%, 2=4,1%, 3=25%, 4=41,6%, and 5=21%.

6) Carabelli's Trait: it is a pronouncement appearing in the lingual face of the Mesio-Lingual cusp or cusp #1 (Protocone). Gradation suggested by Dahlberg (1956, in Turner *et al.*, 1991) and modified by Reid *et al.* (1991). 7 of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degrees 1=50% (See Figure 3), 2=25%, 3=16,7%, and 5=8,3%.

7) Parastyle: it is a pronouncement appearing in the buccal surface of the Mesio-Vestibular cusp or cusp #2 (Paracone). It is recommended to register anyone kind of manifestation in the buccal face of all the molars. Gradation suggested by Bolk (1916 in Turner 1991) and modified by Katich and Turner (1974, in Turner *et al.*, 1991). 14 of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degrees 0=79%, and 1=21%.

Figure 1. Groove Pattern Degree 2 in First Right Lower Premolar belonging to the individual 19 from Obando

8) Groove Pattern: it is the form of the furrows produced by the contact existing among all the cusps. Basic Gradation suggested by Gregory (1916) and modified by Turner (1967, in Turner *et al.*, 1991). Zoubov (1968) also suggests some categories for the patterns Y and +; and Hellman (1928, in Bass, 1995) suggests one category for the pattern X, later modified by Jorgensen (1955, in Bass, 1995). The individuals presented the following frequencies: 15% for Y3, 60% for Y4 (See Figure 2), 10% for Y5, and 15% for X4.

9) Enamel Extension: it is a projection of the enamel edge in apical direction. It is regularly presented in the buccal face. However, it could be present in the other lateral faces. Gradation suggested by Pedersen (1949) and modified by Zoubov (1997). The individuals presented the following degrees 2=40%, 3=15%, and 4=45%.

10) Form of the First Paracone Furrow: it is the form variation of this furrow. Gradation suggested by Zoubov (1997). 9 of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degrees 1=45%, 2=45%, and 3=10%.

11) Position of the First Protocone Furrow: it is the variation in the furrow form. Gradation suggested by Zoubov (1997). 7 of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degrees 1=66,7%, 2=25%, and 3=8,3%.

12) Distal Area Form: it is the furrow variation in this

area of the occlusal surface. Gradation suggested by Zoubov (1997). 10 of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degrees 1=58,8%, 2=17,6%, and 3=26,6%.

13) Reciprocal Position of Furrow 1 of the Paracone and Furrow 2 of the Metacone: it is the form variation of the furrows in the occlusal surface. Gradation suggested by Zoubov (1997). 8 of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degrees 1=42,9%, 2=35,7%, and 3=21,4%.

Lower Molars

14) Protostylid: it is an apex occurring in the buccal face of the cusp #1 (Protoconid). Gradation suggested by Dahlberg (1956, in Turner *et al.*, 1991). 2 of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degree: 1=100%.

15) Distal Trigonid Crest: it is a pronouncement like a loph that joints the cusps #1 and #2 forming a bridge. Gradation suggested by Hanihara (1961, in Turner *et al.*, 1991). 6 of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degree: 1=100%.

16) Deflecting Wrinkle: it is the variation in the cusp #2 or Metaconid form. There is a basic gradation suggested by Sybert and Turner (1975, in Turner *et al.*, 1991). There is another gradation that makes the degree 3 complex in more subdivisions suggested by Wenderich (1937, in Turner *et al.*, 1991) and modified by Susuki, Sakai and Hanihara (1964, in Rodríguez, 1989). In Colombia, Valbuena (1998) suggests other variations of this form, and Zoubov (1997) suggests a gradation different from the previous ones. We used the system suggested by Zoubov (1997). 12

Figure 2. Groove Pattern Y4 belonging to the individual 6 from Obando

Figure 3. Carabelli trait belonging to the individual 6 from Obando

of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degrees 1=26,7%, 2=13,3%, 3=40% (See Figure 4), and 4=20%.

17) Groove Pattern: it is the form of the furrows produced by the existing contact among the cusps. Basic gradation suggested by Gregory (1916 in Turner 1991) and modified by Turner (1967 in Turner 1991). Zoubov (1997) also suggests, some subcategories for the patterns Y and +; and Hellman (1928, in Bass, 1995) suggests one for the pattern X, then modified by Jorgensen (1955, in Bass, 1995). The individuals analyzed presented the following frequencies: 10,3% for Y4, 27,6% for Y5, 14% for Y6, 10,3% for +4, 17,3% for +5, 3,4% for +6, 3,4% for X4, 10,3% for X5, and 3,4% for X6 (Table 1).

18) Cusp Number: the number of cusps in the inferior molars can vary from 4 to 7, each having a specific manifestation number. The basic gradation suggested by Gregory (1916, in Turner *et al.*, 1991) is to register the number of present cusps: 4, 5, 6, or 7. Each of them, called by its given anatomic name, could present different pronouncement degrees. The individuals presented the following frequencies: 4 cusps = 8,3%, 5 cusps = 66,7%, and 6 cusps = 25% (See Table 2).

19) Variation of Cusp #5 or Hipoconulid: it is located in the Disto - Occlusive zone. These degrees are only applied when there is no cusp #6. Gradation suggested by Turner and Warner (1977, in Turner *et al.*, 1991). 18 of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degrees 1=7,4%, 2=26%, 3=29,6%, 4=18,5%, and 5=18,5%.

20) Variation of Cusp #6 or Entoconulid: it is located

in the distal fovea, next to the distal area of the cusp #5. Gradation suggested by Turner (1970, in Turner *et al.*, 1991). 18 of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degrees 0=61,1%, 1=11,1%, 2=22,2%, and 3=5,6%.

21) Enamel Extensions: it is an increase in the enamel edges in apical direction. Gradation suggested by Pedersen (1949, in Turner *et al.*, 1991) and modified by Zoubov (1968). The individuals analyzed presented the following degrees 1=8,3%, 2=25%, 3=8,3%, and

Trait	n	K	Pattern	%
8	20	20	Y3	15
			Y4	60
			Y5	10
			X4	15
17	20	20	Y4	10,3
			Y5	27,6
			Y6	14
			+4	10,3
			+5	17,3
			+6	3,4
			X4	3,4
			X5	10,3
			X6	3,4

Table 1. List of Frequencies of the Groove Pattern in Upper (8) and Lower (7) Molars.

4=58,4% (See Table 3).

22) Metaconid Furrow 2 Position: it is the form variation of this furrow. Gradation suggested by Zoubov (1997). 6 of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degrees 1=22,2%, 2=44,4%, and 3=33,4%.

23) Mutual Position of Protoconid Furrow 1 and Metaconid Furrow 1: it is the form variation of these furrows. Gradation suggested by Zoubov (1997). 8 of the 21 individuals analyzed presented this feature in the degrees 1=44,4%, 2=44,4%, and 3=11,2%.

Discussion

Nowdays, there is no documentation presenting discrete dental trait studies in prehispanic populations of Valle del Cauca Department; the existing documentation of Colombia is limited. This is an obstacle when making morphological comparisons among populations.

The Russian anthropologist A. A. Zoubov, after the analysis of samples from Perú, stated that some dental characteristics of Amerindian dental complex are: high incidence of Shovel – shaped incisors, Deflecting Wrinkle, Entoconulid and low percentage of Carabelli's trait.

Renowned researchers such as Turner, Scott, Hrdlicka, Nelson and Dahlberg (Rodríguez, 1999) agree with the Japanese anthropologist K. Hanihara, who states that the Sinodont division of morphological dental complex is a direct ancestor of the Amerindian dental

Trait	n	k	Cusp	%
18	20	20	4	8,3
			5	66,7
			6	25

Table 2. List of Frequencies of the Number of Cusps in the Lower Molars.

Trait	n	k	Degree	%
9	20	20	2	40
			3	15
			4	45
21	20	20	1	8,3
			2	25
			3	8,3
			4	58,4

Table 3. List of Frequencies relationship of the Length Degree in the Enamel in Upper (9) and Lower (21) Molars.

complex. This also coincides with the hypothesis of North – Asian precedence of the first Americans.

According to these theories, the prehispanic population of Obando show low Carabelli's incidence and high Deflecting Wrinkle and Entoconulid incidence. The Protostylid frequency in the prehispanic population of Obando is too low (10%), which agrees with Zoubov and Turner from this trait.

The existing documents of dental morphology studies about Colombian indigenous populations (León, and Riaño, 1997; Díaz, 1998) let us compare percentages of 6 dental traits (Table 5).

Hypocone: It's present in a very high incidence in 12 Colombian indigenous populations mentioned in written documents (73%). In the prehispanic population of Obando the frequency is moderately high (50%).

Carabelli: The presence of this trait in the Colombian indigenous populations is moderately high (52%) if we consider the A. A. Zoubov analysis (1997) related to low percentages presence of this trait in Amerindian populations. In the prehispanic population of Obando we find a lower incidence (35%). The variation in the establishment of this trait expression degree is high, taking into account the position and dental wear level of upper molars. For the population analyzed, this trait can have variations not observable by the researchers, since the 50% of the sample were under the 20 years of age.

Protostylid: Zoubov (1997) and Turner (1986) consider this trait as a characteristic of Amerindian dental

complex. The Colombian indigenous populations present a very low incidence of this trait (22%), similar to the sample we have studied (10%).

Deflecting Wrinkle: This trait appears in a high incidence (85%) in the Colombian prehispanic populations. In the prehispanic population of Obando, the frequency of this trait is high (60%). The observation of this trait, like the Carabelli's trait, is affected by age and dental wear.

Hypoconulid or Cusp 5: The frequency of this trait in Colombian indigenous populations is considerably low (28%). This does not coincide with the frequency of this trait in the prehispanic population of Obando

	Carabelli	Hipocone	Hipoconulid	Entoconulid	Deflecting Wrinkle	Protostylid
Waunana	50	100	0	0	100	0
Nukak	60	100	0	30	100	60
Chimila	90	100	60	10	80	60
Murui-muinane	50	100	0	0	60	0
Páez Sta. Leticia	30	90	60	30	90	10
Páez	60	100	0	40	100	20
Guambiano	20	100	0	10	80	10
Coreguaje	30	100	100	40	70	20
Guahibo	50	100	100	30	90	0
Wayúú	60	90	50	80	70	40
Guane	60	100	20	20	90	30
Emberá	60	80	10	50	90	20
Obando*	35	50	90	90	60	10

Table 5. Incidence percentages of 6 dental traits in Colombian indigenous populations (from Rodríguez J.V. 1999, except *Obando**).

Figure 4. Groove Pattern and Deflecting Wrinkle Degree 3 belonging to the individual 15 from Obando

Trait	n	k	Degree	%	%(k/n)	è
1	20	7	1	50	35	0.289
			2	50		
2	20	7	1	100	35	0.289
			2	85,8		
3	20	13	1	7,1	65	0.289
			2	85,8		
			3	7,1		
4	20	10	0	10	50	0.047
			1	10		
			3	5		
			4	25		
5	20	10	1	8,3	50	0.047
			2	4,1		
			3	25		
			4	41,6		
			5	21		
6	20	7	1	50	35	0.289
			2	25		
			3	16,7		
7	20	14	1	21	70	0.420
			2	79		
			3	8,3		
10	20	9	1	45	45	0.094
			2	45		
			3	10		
11	20	7	1	66,7	35	0.289
			2	25		
			3	8,3		
12	20	10	1	58,8	50	0.047
			2	17,6		
			3	26,6		
13	20	8	1	42,9	40	0.191
			2	35,7		
			3	21,4		
14	20	2	1	100	10	0.868
			2	100	30	0.390
16	20	12	1	26,7	60	0.191
			2	13,3		
			3	40		
			4	20		
19	20	18	1	7,4	90	0.868
			2	26		
			3	29,6		
			4	18,5		
			5	18,5		
20	20	18	0	61,1	90	0.868
			1	11,1		
			2	22,2		
			3	5,6		
22	20	6	1	22,2	30	0.390
			2	44,4		
			3	33,4		
23	20	8	1	44,4	40	0.191
			2	44,4		
			3	11,2		

Table 4. List of Frequency of the Possible Traits for Angular Transformation

(90%).

Entoconulid or Cusp 6: This trait presents a low frequency in Colombian indigenous populations (46%). This does not coincide with the high frequency of this trait in the prehispanic population of Obando (90%).

Conclusions

The observation of the dental pieces belonging to the prehispanic population of Obando, carrier of the *Quimbaya Tardío* cultural tradition who lived in the year 780 +/- 110 AD. Allowed us to precisely analyze 23 discrete dental traits whose description we have presented in this article.

The bibliographical references studied just allow us to compare the prehispanic population of Obando with other 12 Colombian indigenous populations by using only 6 traits. The comparison of these six traits let us observe differences in the frequency of all traits, especially in Hipoconulid and Entoconulid traits.

The Protostylid trait presented in a very low incidence in the prehispanic population of Obando does not correspond with the analysis mentioned by Zoubov (1997) and Turner (1986) from this trait in Amerindian populations.

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